

MEDICAL SCIENCES

CHILDHOOD ASTHMA. DIAGNOSTIC AND THERAPEUTIC PROBLEMS. GINA 2024 RECOMMENDATIONS

Abdulhamid A.K.

D.M., pediatrician and pediatric pulmonologist at the pediatric department, multidisciplinary hospital for active treatment "Uni Hospital" - city of Panagyurishte, Bulgaria

Abstract

Childhood asthma is the most common chronic disease in childhood (12-14%) worldwide and 3-10% of asthmatics suffer from severe asthma. Despite the enormous progress in the diagnosis and treatment of childhood asthma, there are still some challenges in terms of diagnosis, as well as in the selection of adequate and timely maintenance treatment, which remain problematic. Overdiagnosis leads to unnecessary drug therapy and associated side effects, and on the other hand, underdiagnosis carries the risk of daily symptoms, potentially serious exacerbations and long-term remodeling of the airways and unnecessary use of antibiotics to treat the so-called "recurrent respiratory infections with BOS". Furthermore, the use of a personalized asthma action plan (PAAP) remains limited and a significant number of children with asthma do not have one and over 70-80% of asthma patients do not use their inhaler correctly. The population goal of asthma management is to prevent deaths from asthma and to minimize the burden of asthma on individuals, families, communities, health systems and the environment.

Keywords: Childhood asthma - diagnosis, over- and under-diagnosis, differential diagnosis, management, PAAPs.

Abbreviations

BOS: broncho-obstructive syndrome
 GERD: gastroesophageal reflux disease
 TSLP: Thymic stromal lymphopoietin
 DD: differential diagnosis
 OCS: oral corticosteroids
 ICS: inhaled corticosteroid
 SABA: short-acting beta2 agonist
 HDM SLIT: home dust mite sublingual immunotherapy
 PAAPs: personalized asthma action plans
 MART: maintenance and reliever Therapy
 pMDI: pressurized metered-dose inhaler
 RF: respiratory failure

Introduction:

Childhood asthma is a heterogeneous disease usually characterized by chronic airway inflammation. This is determined by a history of respiratory symptoms such as wheezing, difficulty breathing, chest tightness, and cough of varying variability, frequency, and intensity, along with variable expiratory airflow obstruction^[4]. These variations are often triggered by triggers such as exercise, exposure to an allergen or irritant, weather changes, or viral respiratory infections. Asthma is associated with hyperreactivity and airway inflammation, but these are not necessary or sufficient for the diagnosis. Risk factors for the development of asthma in childhood include: Personal or family history of atopy (eczema, allergic rhinitis or nasal polyposis); Family history of asthma; Exposure to cigarette smoke; Premature birth; Low birth weight; Obesity; Bronchopulmonary dysplasia; Respiratory infections – bronchiolitis; Home allergens (dust, animal hair, cockroaches, mold); Air pollution (outdoor allergens – pollens, spores, industrial chemicals, insects).^{[3][4]}

Asthma exacerbations usually occur after exposure to one or more triggers. The most frequent

triggers of an asthma attack are: Viral infections of the respiratory tract; Physical effort; Meteorological changes in temperature and humidity; Household contaminants (e.g. pests, mold and mites); Environmental pollutants (e.g. air pollution); Exposure to secondhand smoke; Pets and animals; Strong odors; Anxiety or strong emotions; Medicines (e.g. non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs and beta-blockers); Gastroesophageal reflux.^{[4] [24] [25] [1,27]}

For individuals with asthma of all ages, the goal of asthma management is to achieve the best possible long-term patient outcomes, including: Few/or no asthma symptoms; No sleep disturbances due to asthma; Unimpaired physical activity; No exacerbations; Improved or stable personal best lung function; No OCS support requirement; There are no side effects from the medication. The patient's goals for their asthma may be different from medical goals; and patients with few or no asthma symptoms can have severe or fatal exacerbations, including from external triggers such as viral infections, allergen exposure (if sensitized) or pollution^[4]. In allergic asthma, most cells exhibit a T-cell helper type 2 (Th2) cytokine secretion profile (IL1, IL4, IL5, IL9, and GM-CSF). Biomarkers of type 2 inflammation include eosinophils in sputum and blood, levels of exhaled nitric oxide (FeNO), and serum periostin. However, some patients do not exhibit eosinophilic inflammation and a Th2 cytokine response and are less responsive to ICS and other medications targeting Th2 cytokines, and they have a predominantly mononuclear inflammatory cell response in the airways, with T lymphocytes and activated macrophages^[4]. Potential applications of biomarkers in severe asthma^[55] include: Understanding the biology; Diagnosis and screening; Assessment of severity, control, or prognosis; Identification of endotypes; Application in clinical trials and safety monitoring. Regarding the assessment of asthma control, GINA 2024 clarified that

the assessment of symptom control cannot be limited to the last 4 weeks, but there are no validated instruments to assess symptom control for a longer period than this. GINA continues to emphasize that the assessment of symptom control is not sufficient and that patients' risk factors for exacerbations, accelerated decline in lung function, and adverse drug effects should also be assessed.^{[4] [23] [26] [28] [29] [30]}

Assessment of asthma control in adults, adolescents, and children 6-11 years of age^[4] includes:

1. Recent symptom control. In the past 4 weeks, has the patient had:

- Daytime asthma symptoms more than twice a week?
- Any nighttime awakenings due to asthma?
- SABA reliever for symptoms more than twice a week?
- Is there any activity limitation due to asthma?

Absence of any of the above criteria indicates well-controlled asthma; 1-2 of them indicates partially controlled asthma; and the presence of 3 - 4 of these criteria indicates uncontrolled asthma.

2. Risk factors for poor asthma outcomes. Assess risk factors at diagnosis and periodically, especially in patients with exacerbations, and measure FEV1 at baseline, after 3-6 months of ICS-containing treatment to determine the patient's best lung function, then periodically for ongoing risk assessment.

a. **Risk factors for exacerbations** are: Uncontrolled asthma symptoms; High SABA use($\geq 3 \times 200$

canisters/year are associated with an increased risk of exacerbations and ≥ 1 canister/month increases the risk of mortality); Unprescribed ICS, poor adherence or incorrect inhaler technique; Obesity, chronic rhino-sinusitis, GERD, confirmed food allergy, pregnancy; Smoking, e-cigarette, allergen exposure during sensitization, air pollution; Major psychological or socioeconomic problems; Low FEV1 (especially $< 60\%$ predicted), high bronchodilator response; Type 2 inflammatory markers (higher blood eosinophils, high FeNO in adults with allergic asthma on ICS); Exacerbation history (≥ 1 severe exacerbation in the past year, ever intubated or in an asthma intensive care unit).

b. **Risk factors for permanent airflow limitation, include:** History of preterm birth, low birth weight and greater infant weight gain, chronic mucus hypersecretion; Lack of ICS treatment in patients with a history of severe exacerbation; Tobacco smoke, noxious chemicals; occupational or household exposures; Low baseline FEV1, sputum or blood eosinophilia.

c. **Risk factors for adverse drug reactions, include:** Frequent OCS, long-term, high-dose and/or potent ICS, P450 inhibitors and poor inhaler technique.

Differential diagnosis (DD) of asthma.

Before making a diagnosis of "asthma", a thorough differential diagnosis should first be performed, taking into account the most common alternative diagnoses^[1], Table 1^[4]

Table 1

Differential diagnosis (DD) of asthma by age.

Up to 5 years old	Recurrent viral infections of the respiratory system; Gastroesophageal reflux; Foreign body aspiration; Persistent bacterial bronchitis; Tracheomalacia; Tuberculosis; Pertussis; Congenital heart disease; Cystic fibrosis; Primary ciliary dyskinesia; "Vascular ring"; Bronchopulmonary dysplasia; Immune deficiency.
6 – 11 years	Chronic upper respiratory tract cough syndrome (posterior nasal drip syndrome); Aspirated foreign body; Bronchiectasis; Primary ciliary dyskinesia; Congenital heart disease (CHD), Bronchopulmonary dysplasia and Cystic fibrosis.
≥ 12 years of age	Chronic upper airway cough syndrome; Inducible laryngeal obstruction; Hyperventilation and dysfunctional breathing; Bronchiectasis, Cystic fibrosis; CHD; Alpha1-antitrypsin deficiency; Foreign body aspiration.

Asthma diagnosis.

Diagnosing asthma in childhood can be challenging, and the diagnosis should be reviewed during follow-up to ensure it is correct. It should be emphasized that there is no single "gold standard" test that can be used to accurately diagnose asthma. In practice, diagnosis should be made based on characteristic symptoms, evidence of variability in airflow limitation in the presence of airway inflammation, exclusion of alternative diagnoses, and response to treatment. Making the correct diagnosis is key to optimal management of childhood asthma. Guidelines vary across countries and regions regarding diagnostic criteria.^{[1][4][54]}

The main steps in diagnosing asthma include:

- History of persistent and recurrent symptoms of bronchial obstruction (cough, wheezing and/or chest tightness, difficulty breathing) and family history of atopy (allergic rhinitis, atopic dermatitis, asthma).

- Physical examination. Physical examination is often normal in patients with asthma unless the disease is severe or the examination is performed during an exacerbation. In the latter cases, "wheezing" can be heard on auscultation, with prolonged exhalation or signs of severe bronchial obstruction (tachypnea, dyspnea, tachycardia, and in advanced RF, cyanosis, retractions and impaired consciousness are also noticed).

- **Functional testing of breathing.** The diagnosis of asthma also requires objective measurements to support the diagnosis. Peak expiratory flow (PEF) and spirometry are commonly used to assess the severity of airflow obstruction and reversibility (after inhalation of SABA). PEF-metry can also be used to detect diurnal variation, which is a typical feature of asthma, and is the most useful test in severe and labile (unstable) asthma. Although PEF is less reliable than spirometry in aiding the diagnosis of asthma, it can be relied upon rather than relying on symptoms alone.^[4] The

Global Initiative for Asthma (GINA) specifically recommends the use of either PEF or spirometry in the diagnosis of asthma in children over 5 years of age. Objective testing should be repeated if there is poor response to treatment or diagnostic uncertainty. A reduced FEV1 with a low FEV1/FVC ratio (forced expiratory volume in 1 second/forced vital capacity) indicates the presence of airway obstruction. Significant reversibility after bronchodilator administration is generally defined as an increase in FEV1 of $\geq 12\%$ and at least a 200 ml change. With regular ICS treatment, FEV1 begins to improve within days and reaches a plateau after about 2 months. The patients' highest FEV1 reading (personal best) should be documented, as this provides a more useful comparison for clinical practice than predicted percentage. If FEV1 predicted values are used, GINA recommends measuring children's height at each visit. In children under 5 years of age, pulmonary function testing is rarely practical outside of a research setting, making diagnosis in this age group an additional challenge.^[4]

- BPT (Broncho-provocation tests) - "direct" and "indirect". "Direct" include the pharmacological agents - histamine and methacholine (an analog of acetylcholine)^[19]. But it is assumed that the bronchial hyper-responsiveness (BHR) induced by them is not specific for the diagnosis of asthma, since healthy people without asthma^{[4][7][20]}, patients with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease^{[21][22]}, as well as smokers may also have hyper-reactivity to these agents^[23]. "Indirect" tests include physical stimuli such as exercise, hyperventilation with dry air, distilled water, hypertonic NaCl, mannitol, and the pharmacological agent adenosine monophosphate. It is suggested that these stimuli cause narrowing of the airways by an "indirect" mechanism through the release of various mediators from inflammatory cells in the bronchi themselves, these mediators subsequently activating their specific receptors in the bronchial smooth muscle, which consequently contracts and leads to narrowing of the airways^[26].

- FeNO - test. FeNO is a practical, rapidly performed test in school-aged children and provides information about the severity of lung inflammation. The primary role of FeNO in clinical practice continues to be to aid in treatment decisions in patients with severe asthma, i.e., it is used to detect and quantify eosinophilic airway inflammation, with elevated levels in patients with eosinophilic asthma.^[54] According to GINA^[4], FeNO has not been shown to be useful in making or ruling out a diagnosis of asthma, as while FeNO is higher in asthma characterized by type 2 airway inflammation (with elevated interleukin (IL)-4 and IL13), FeNO is also elevated in non-asthmatic conditions (e.g., eosinophilic bronchitis, atopy, allergic rhinitis, eczema) and is not elevated in some asthma phenotypes (e.g., neutrophilic asthma, obesity-related asthma). FeNO is low in smokers and during bronchoconstriction and the early phases of an allergic response, and may be elevated or decreased during viral respiratory infections.^[4]

Criteria for the initial diagnosis of asthma in adults, adolescents and children aged 6 to 11 years^[4] include:

1. History of typical variable respiratory symptoms, including wheezing; shortness of breath; chest tightness and cough. Provided that the symptoms appear variable over time and with different severity; often worse at night or upon awakening; they are often triggered by exercise, laughter, allergens, cold air, and often occur or worsen with a viral infection.

2. Confirmed variable expiratory airflow limitation. Established excessive variability in expiratory lung function in the presence of one or more of the following measurements:

- Positive bronchodilator test for reversibility of bronchial obstruction with spirometry or PEF (peak expiratory flow rate assessed by peak flow meter). Asthma is characterized by marked or complete reversibility of bronchial obstruction, this is a fact when in children the values of FEV1 increase $\geq 12\%$ or PEF $\geq 15\%$ (highest value of 3 measurements) from their initial value, 10-15 minutes after 200 - 400 mcg Salbutamol or equivalent and provided that bronchodilator treatment has been discontinued before the test (≥ 4 hours for SABA and 24-48 hours for LABA). This variability is related to underlying BHR and inflammation.

- Excessive variability in PEF measured twice daily for 2 weeks, resulting in an average daily PEF variability of more than 13% in children.

- Improvement of lung function after 4 weeks of CS treatment - content. For children, a positive result is obtained with increased values of FEV1 $\geq 12\%$ predicted (or PEF $\geq 15\%$) of the baseline value.

- Positive BPT test in children, if results in reduced FEV1 values $> 12\%$ predicted (or reduction in PEF $\geq 15\%$) of the baseline value after a standard physical effort test. If FEV1 decreases during a challenge test, verify that the FEV1/FVC ratio also decreases, as incomplete inspiration, due to possible laryngeal obstruction or poor effort, may cause a false decrease in FEV1.

- Excessive variation in lung function between visits (good specificity but poor sensitivity) in children, was defined as a change in FEV1 of $\geq 12\%$ predicted (or in PEF $\geq 15\%$) between visits. As with PEF measurements, the highest value of three trials should be selected.

Asthma phenotypes.

A phenotype is the visible structural and functional characteristics of an organism, determined by its genotype and modulated by environment," Rice JP et al. *Adv Genet* 2001. Endotype is "a subtype of a condition that is defined by different functional or pathophysiological mechanisms," Lötvall et al. *JACI* 2011. Phenotypes reflect the heterogeneity of asthma. Asthma is a heterogeneous disease with several phenotypes and underlying endotypes. Phenotypes are subtypes of asthma that share clinical characteristics such as symptoms, atopic features, disease severity, and response to treatment. Endotypes are subtypes of asthma that are characterized by similar underlying biological mechanisms.^[37] Key endotypes include asthma - inflammation type 2-high and type 2-low.^[50] Identification of asthma phenotypes and endotypes may facilitate targeted treatment based on the pathophysiology occurring in a particular individual^[38] for example, allergic

or eosinophilic asthma, which often begins in childhood is type 2-high and is characterized by eosinophilic airway inflammation, elevated IgE and fractional levels of exhaled nitric oxide (FeNO)^[36]. Typically, high-type 2 asthma responds well to inhaled corticosteroid (ICS) treatment.^[51] According to GINA^[4], asthma is a heterogeneous disease with distinct underlying disease processes and recognizable groups of demographic, clinical and/or pathophysiological characteristics, often referred to as “asthma phenotypes”. Some phenotype-specific treatments are available for patients with more severe asthma. However, except in patients with severe asthma, no strong association between specific pathological features and specific clinical patterns or responses to treatment has been found, and more research is needed to understand the clinical utility of phenotypic classification in asthma. Many clinical phenotypes of asthma have been identified, some of the most common of which are:

- **Allergic asthma.** This is the most easily recognized asthma phenotype, which often begins in childhood and is associated with past and/or family history of allergic diseases, such as eczema, allergic rhinitis, and food or drug allergy. Examination of sputum from these patients before treatment often reveals eosinophilic inflammation of the airways. Patients with this asthma phenotype usually respond well to ICS treatment.

- **Non-allergic asthma.** Some patients have asthma that is not associated with an allergy. The sputum cellular profile of these patients may be neutrophilic, eosinophilic, or contain few inflammatory cells. Patients with non-allergic asthma often respond less well to ICS.

- **Cough variant of asthma.** The cough variant as a clinical phenotype of asthma can hardly be distinguished from other causes of chronic cough in clinical practice, as spirometry is normal and variable expiratory airflow obstruction can only be identified by **BPT**. Some patients subsequently also develop “wheezing” and a bronchodilator reaction. And the treatment of the cough variant of bronchial asthma is the same as for asthma in general. Responds well to ICS-containing treatment.^[4] This phenotype must be distinguished from the cough syndrome of URT, which is associated with diseases such as chronic rhinosinusitis, gastroesophageal reflux disease (GERD), etc.^[1]

- **Late-onset asthma** (asthma in adults). Some adults (especially women) present with asthma for the first time in late life. These patients are usually non-allergic, and often require higher doses of ICS or are relatively refractory to CS treatment.

- **Asthma with fixed airflow obstruction (FAO).** Some patients with long - standing asthma develop persistent or irreversible FAO.

- **Asthma with obesity.** Some obese patients have asthma with pronounced symptoms and mild eosinophilic inflammation of the airways.

- **Exercise Asthma.** Sometimes symptoms induced by physical exertion are the only manifestation of asthma. In this regard, the term exercise-induced asthma has been proposed to describe the occurrence of transient airway narrowing after exercise.

Treatment.

Effective asthma management involves a comprehensive approach aimed at both pharmacological and non-pharmacological control. The latter includes education on how to undertake effective treatment, avoidance of triggers, modifiable risk factors and actions to be taken during acute attacks through personalized asthma action plans (PAAP), consideration of the cost of treatment, patient preferences and treatment of comorbidities (chronic rhino-sinusitis, GERD, etc.) and last but not least at each stage of treatment, if asthma control is not maintained, the patient should be monitored for therapy and inhaler treatment technique. PAAPs have been shown to reduce emergency room visits and missed school days and increase caregiver confidence in managing asthma attacks.^[55] Age and phenotype-specific characteristics are important in individualizing the approach.^[13]

Pharmacological treatment includes two main groups of medications (medications to relieve acute symptoms and medications to control asthma).

a. **Quick-relief medications** to relieve acute asthma symptoms such as wheezing, chest tightness, and coughing during exacerbations of all forms of childhood asthma. This group includes:

- **Short-Acting β_2 -agonists (SABA)** in adequate doses are the drug of choice, especially in children up to 5 years of age. The inhaler route of administration is preferred. While for adults, teenagers and children from 6 to 11 years a combination of ICS – Formoterol / beclomethasone is recommended as fixed-dose combination within the MART plan ^[4] ^[15]

- **Short-acting (SAMA) muscarinic antagonists.** Inhaled muscarinic receptor antagonists (IMA), also called M-cholinolytics fall into two groups: short-acting (SAMA) and long-acting (LAMA) muscarinic antagonists. IMAs are competitive antagonists of acetylcholine versus muscarinic receptors, so they selectively reduce or eliminate parasympathetic stimulation, therefore reducing bronchial spasm, bronchial mucus secretion, and inhibiting bronchial expectoration. SAMA(the main representative is Ipratropium bromide) are the second important group of drugs that are recommended for pharmacological control as inhaled bronchodilators in asthma and are mainly recommended in patients who either do not tolerate or have insufficient effect from SABA treatment. Ipratropium bromide usually used in combination with SABA in acute asthma. ^[31] ^[32] ^[33] ^[34] ^[35]

- **Methylxanthines.** Theophylline is a major representative and has modest bronchodilator activity, and its use in the treatment of asthma is limited due to concerns about toxicity and less efficacy than other long-term control agents.

- **Systemic corticosteroids.** Systemic corticosteroids do not cause rapid bronchodilation, but nevertheless they are used in view of their strong anti-inflammatory effect for the treatment of more severe asthmatic exacerbations.

Treatment of asthma exacerbations for adults, adolescents and children aged 6-11 years.

First, the severity of the exacerbation must be determined.

- In a mild or moderate-severe asthmatic exacerbation patient speaks phrases, prefers to sit or lie down, does not disturbed, does not use accessory respiratory muscles when breathing, increased respiratory rate; Pulse - 100 - 120 b/min.; O₂ saturation (on air) 90 - 95%; PEF more than 50% predicted or best. In this case, start treatment with 4 - 10 puffs of salbutamol (albuterol) metered dose aerosol with a spacer or 5 mg with nebulizer every 20 minutes during the 1st hour. In case of insufficient effect, prednisolone is administered (for adults: 40-50 mg, and for children > 6 years: 1-2 mg/kg, max. 40 mg); oxygen therapy to a target O₂-saturation of 93-95% (for children: 94-98%). If there is no effect, continue the treatment with SABA (4-10 puffs every 3-4 hours to 6-10 puffs every 1-2 hours). On improvement, assess for discharge if: Symptoms improved, no need for SABA; Improved PEF, and > 60% predicted or best; O₂ saturation above 94% in atmospheric air; Adequate resources at home.

- If the patient's condition worsens despite the treatment provided so far or in case of severe asthma exacerbation (patient sits hunched forward, excited or sleepy, confused, with respiratory rate over 30/min, pulse - over 120 beats /min, activated accessory muscles; O₂ saturation (in air) < 90%; PEF ≤ 50% predicted or best), while waiting for transfer to emergency care, continue SABA, give ipratropium bromide (500 µg via nebulizer/20 minutes or 4-8 puffs/20 minutes with pMDI and spacer for 1 hour, then, if necessary), systemic corticosteroids and O₂ therapy.

b. Asthma maintenance medications. They are used daily for a long time to achieve and maintain asthma control and include:

- **Inhaled and systemic corticoids.** Corticosteroids, especially ICS, are agents of first choice for the maintenance treatment of asthma. Corticosteroids have a powerful anti-inflammatory effect, reduce bronchial hyper-reactivity, mucus secretion and swelling of mucous membranes, increase the number of beta – adrenergic receptors in the lungs and increase their sensitivity to the action of β₂-agonists. The use of oral or systemic corticosteroids increases the risk of fractures [16,15]. It is recommended to check the height of children with asthma treated with ICS at least once a year (GINA 2018). ICS are the most effective anti-inflammatory therapy in the treatment of childhood asthma and are used to control persistent asthma regardless of severity [15][3]. Early initiation of ICS modifies the course of the disease [17]. ICS reduce symptoms, exacerbations and prevent airway remodeling, reduce mortality and morbidity in asthma, Daily doses of ICS by age are given in **table 2 and 3** [19][4]. Although ICS significantly reduces asthma exacerbations and serious exacerbations in patients not taking ICS are associated with greater decline in lung function, there is no clear evidence that ICS use prevents the long-term development of permanent airflow limitation [4]. When high-dose ICS are offered as a treatment option for adults and adolescents, it is again stated that this is for short-term use only, e.g. for 3–6 months, to minimize the potential for side effect [4].

- **Leukotriene modifiers (LTRA).** LTRAs include montelukast and zafirlukast. These medications

are recommended in the treatment of mild and moderate asthma as adjunctive treatment in children with asthma not fully controlled by ICS [15, 21].

- **Long-acting beta₂-agonists (LABA).** LABAs include salmeterol, formoterol and others, which are inhaled bronchodilators that improve airflow by relieving obstruction for 12 – 24 hours. They should not be used alone in asthma for safety reasons and are usually given in combination with ICS (budesonide - formoterol; fluticasone - salmeterol and mometasone – formoterol). When used in combination with ICSs, LABAs lead to greater control of asthma and exacerbations. [22]

- **Long - acting muscarinic antagonist (LAMA).** The main representative is Tiotropium bromide. This group of drugs is recommended as additional treatment in step 4 in children aged 6 - 11 years and in steps 4 and 5 in adults and children ≥ 12 years.

- **Cromolyns.** They are non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs that inhibit the release of mast cell mediators. Cromolyn group drugs exhibit an anti-inflammatory effect associated with stabilization of the mast cell membrane and are now less often used to control asthma. Representatives of this group are sodium cromoglycate (cromolyn sodium), nedocromil sodium. [2]

- **Immunotherapy** (desensitization, allergen immunotherapy). It can be part of the complex treatment of mild and moderately severe asthma in children over 5 years. The development of an allergy to an otherwise harmless antigen such as pollen or dust mite is called sensitization. Desensitization is the treatment that aims to reduce sensitivity and reactivity to the allergen. Immunotherapy consists of administering the allergen to which the patient is allergic, with increasing doses. The goal is to modulate the immune system by increasing case-specific regulatory T lymphocytes. The therapy is carried out with subcutaneous injections or sublingually (sublingually - there are tablets and drops).

- **Biological therapy** (monoclonal antibodies). Biologic therapy with monoclonal antibodies targets inflammatory cytokines (interleukins, GM - CSF and others), which are biologically active mediators involved in the pathogenesis of asthma and responsible for the symptoms of the disease (bronchial inflammation, bronchospasm, hypersecretion). These medications are administered by injection at 2- to 8-week intervals in addition to standard control treatment. They mainly lead to a reduction in the number of exacerbations and the dose of ICS, as well as to a varying degree to an improvement in lung function and quality of life [44,45]. They are mainly recommended for patients with severe asthma (in Step 5)[4]. The following monoclonal antibodies are authorized for use in Bulgaria:

- Omalizumab (anti-IgE) is an immunomodulator available as an injectable monoclonal antibody that binds to IgE, thereby preventing it from binding to its receptor. Currently, omalizumab is mainly recommended for patients with severe asthma in adults and children over 12 years of age and for those for whom there is evidence of IgE-dependent asthma (positive skin test or serological evidence of allergen-specific IgE). Long-term safety and efficacy in children with asthma have not been well studied.

- Mepolizumab (anti IL-5). It is indicated for the treatment of severe eosinophilic asthma in adults and children over 6 years of age.

- Benralizumab (anti CD125). It is indicated in severe eosinophilic asthma in adults only.

Table 2

Inhaled corticosteroids - daily doses for children over 12 years.

Medicine	Low doses	Moderate doses	High doses
Beclomethasone dipropionate (standard particle)	200-500 µg	>500-1000 µg	>1000 µg
Beclomethasone dipropionate (extrafine particle)	100 – 200 µg	> 200 – 400 µg	> 400 µg
Budesonide(standard particle)	200-400 µg	> 200-800 µg	>800 µg
Ciclesonide(extrafine particle)	80 -160 µg	>160 -320 µg	> 320 µg
Fluticasone propionate	100-200 µg	> 200-500 µg	>500 µg

Table 3

Inhaled corticosteroids - daily doses for children aged 6-11 years.

Медикамент	Low doses	Moderate doses	High doses
Beclomethasone dipropionate (standard particle)	100-200 µg	>200- 400 µg	> 400 µg
Beclomethasone dipropionate (extrafine particle)	50 – 100 µg	> 100 – 200 µg	> 200 µg
Budesonide(standard particle)	100-200 µg	> 200-400 µg	>400 µg
Budesonide(nebules)	250 – 500 µg	> 500 – 1000	>1000
Ciclesonide(extrafine particle)	80 µg	>80 -160 µg	>160 µg
Fluticasone propionate	50 – 100 µg	>100-200 µg	>200 µg

Stages of treatment in adults and adolescents diagnosed with asthma ^[4]:

First, assess patients' symptom control and their risk factors for exacerbations, for decreased lung function, and for adverse drug reactions.

Second, adjust patient management based on these assessments. This includes education and skills training and, adjusting medications as needed, treating modifiable risk factors causing exacerbations and concomitant diseases (rhino-sinusitis, allergic rhinitis, GERD, food allergy, obesity, anxiety and depression), relevant non-pharmacological strategies (physical activity, healthy diet including fruits and vegetables, smoking cessation, pulmonary rehabilitation programs, avoiding medications that would worsen asthma, reducing body weight, breathing exercises, avoiding exposure to external allergens, household and occupational irritants and allergens, avoidance of pollutants in closed facilities/atmospheric conditions, avoidance of food - allergens).

Third - examine the patient in accordance with the goals of treatment.

Stepwise control depends on the severity of asthma (GINA 2024) in steps from 1 to 5, table 4 and 5.

- Mild asthma is asthma that is well controlled with low-intensity treatment, i.e. low-dose ICS or SABA, as needed.

- Moderate asthma is asthma that is well controlled on Step 3 or Step 4.

- Severe asthma is asthma that remains uncontrolled despite optimal treatment with high-dose ICS-LABA or asthma that requires high-dose ICS-LABA to prevent it from becoming uncontrolled. Before making a diagnosis of severe asthma, the following should be ruled out: poor inhaler technique, lack of adherence to treatment, misdiagnosis of asthma, multiple comorbidities, or prolonged exposure to sensitizing or irritating agents in the home or work environment, including tobacco smoke.

- Labile (unstable) asthma. Presents with sudden life-threatening attacks without prodromes. Unlike milder asthma, labile asthma tends to be resistant to inhaled corticosteroids.

In patients with persistent symptoms and/or exacerbations despite high-dose ICS therapy (with good adherence and correct inhalation technique), the clinical or inflammatory phenotype should be assessed, as this may guide the choice of additional treatment, which may include LAMAs, LTRAs, low-dose azithromycin (adults), and biologic agents for severe asthma. And in patients with severe asthma, allergen immunotherapy may be considered as an adjunctive treatment, but only after asthma symptoms and exacerbations have been controlled.^[4] For safety reasons, GINA does not recommend treating asthma with SABA alone in adults, adolescents, and children aged 6 – 12 years. They should instead receive treatment containing ICS to reduce their risk of serious exacerbations and to control symptoms. And for children who are unlikely to adhere to ICS maintenance therapy, ICS can be taken whenever the child uses their reliever SABA. A common question is which patients should start treatment at step 3, i.e. with low-dose ICS - formoterol taken as MART, there is no specific evidence to support this choice, but clinical factors in which it is recommended to consider initiation of MART include symptoms every day, currently smoking, low lung function, recent severe exacerbation or history of life-threatening exacerbation. GINA (2024) recommends Daily maintenance treatment is recommended only from Step 3 for all ages, but in children up to 5 years (double low-dose ICS) is allowed only after a confirmed diagnosis of asthma and lacks the effect of low-dose ICS maintenance treatment in step 2 and also recommends possible addition of LAMA in children from 6 – 11 years in Step 4 and in step 4 and 5 in in adults and children ≥12 years and medium doses of ICS – formoterol or medium/high doses of ICS-LABA and high dose ICS – formoterol only for adults and children ≥12 years in step 5.

Table 4.

Stepwise personalized asthma management for adults and adolescents over 12 years to control symptoms and minimize future risk.

If the patient has	Steps	Start with Track 1 (Preferred)	Track 2	Other controller options
In case of lack of control of symptoms in step 4	5	Add-on LAMA Refer for assessment of phenotype. Consider high dose ICS - formoterol maintenance +- anti - IgE, anti - IL5/5R, anti - IL4Ra, anti- TSLP	Add-on LAMA Refer for assessment of phenotype. Consider high dose ICS - LABA maintenance +- anti - IgE, anti - IL5/5R, anti - IL4Ra,anti-	Add azithromycin (adults) or add LTRA, consider adding low dose OCS but consider side -effects
Daily symptoms waking at night once a week or more and low lung function, or recent exacerbation	4	Medium dose ICS - formoterol maintenance and reliever(MART)	Medium/high dose ICS-LABA + as - needed SABA (or ICS - SABA)	Add LAMA or add LTRA, or add HDM SLIT, or switch to high dose ICS - only. Note: Short course of OCS may also be needed for patients presenting during an exacerbation
Symptoms most days waking at night once a week or more and low lung function	3	Low dose ICS - formoterol maintenance and reliever(MART)	Low dose ICS - LABA + as -needed SABA (or ICS - SABA)	Medium dose ICS or add LTRA, or add HDM SLIT
Symptoms less than 3 -5 days a week, with normal (or mildly reduced) lung function	2	As-needed-only Low dose ICS - formoterol	Step 2: Low dose ICS + as needed SABA (or ICS -SABA)	other options common to step 1 and 2: low dose ICS whenever SABA is taken or daily LTRA, or add HDM SLIT Note: In patients with symptoms 1-2 days a week or less, adherence with daily ICS would be very poor, so taking low dose ICS whenever SABA is taken could reduce the risk of exacerbations
	1		Step 1: Take low dose ICS whenever SABA is taken	

Stepwise personalized asthma management for children aged 6–11 years to control symptoms and minimize future risk.

If the patient has	Steps	Start with	Notes	Other controller options
No symptom control on step 4	Step 5	Refer for phenotypic assessment. Consider high dose ICS - LABA or add-on therapy, e.g. +- anti - IgE, , anti - IL4Ra, anti - IL5		As last resort, consider add-on low dose OCS but consider side -effects
Symptoms most days waking at night once or more a week and low lung function,	step 4	Refer for expert advice, or medium dose ICS – LABA plus as – needed SABA or low - dose MART	Short course of OCS may also be needed for patients presenting during an exacerbation	Add tiotropium or add LTRA
Symptoms most days waking at night once or more a week	step 3	Low dose ICS – LABA or medium -dose ICS plus as-needed SABA; or very-low - dose MART		Low dose ICS + LTRA
Symptoms 2 – 5 days a week,	Step 2	Daily Low dose ICS plus as-needed SABA	In patients with symptoms 1 -2 days a week or less, adherence with daily ICS is likely to be very poor, so taking low dose ICS whenever SABA is taken may be a better option for reducing exacerbation risk	Daily LTRA, or low dose ICS whenever SABA is taken
Symptoms less than 2 days a week	Step 1	Take low dose ICS whenever SABA is taken		

Note: when assessing the response to 3 – 6 months asthma treatment, review: Symptom control; exacerbations since previous visit; and how they were managed; medication side-effects; Inhaler technique and adherence; Lung function; Patient satisfaction and concerns. The possibility of refractory type 2 inflammation should be considered if any of the following are found while the patient is taking high – dose ICS or daily OCS: Blood eosinophils ≥ 150 /mcl, and or FeNO ≥ 20 ppb, and or Sputum eosinophils $\geq 2\%$, and or Asthma is clinically allergen – driven.

Causes of asthma treatment failure include: Poor inhaler technique; Lack of cooperation or poor adherence to the therapeutic regimen; Inadequate choice of anti-inflammatory medication or inappropriate dose; Poor control of the underlying inflammation from the dose of steroid used; Inadequate education of the patient and/or caregivers; Environmental triggers; Over diagnosis (especially in children under 2 years old).

Spirometric criteria for hospitalization or discharge from the emergency department ^[4]:

- Hospitalization is recommended if pre-treatment FEV1 or PEF is less than 25% predicted or personal best, or post-treatment FEV1 or PEF is less than 40% predicted or personal best.

- If lung function after treatment is 40 – 60% predicted, discharge may be possible after assessment of patient risk factors and availability of follow-up care.

- If pulmonary function after treatment is greater than 60% predicted or personal best, discharge is recommended after assessment of patient risk factors and availability of follow-up care.

Other factors associated with an increased likelihood of needing hospital treatment include:

- Female, elderly, non-white
- Use of more than 8 beta 2 agonist puffs in the previous 24 hours.
- Severe exacerbation (e.g., tachypnea, need for resuscitation or rapid medical intervention on arrival, O2 saturation < 95%, final PEF less than 50%)
- Past history of severe exacerbation (e.g., intubations, asthma hospitalizations)
- Previous unscheduled office and emergency department visits required use of OCS.

Recommendations to refer patients for expert advice when and where possible ^[4] in the following cases:

1. Difficulty in confirming the diagnosis of asthma (inconclusive objective tests, lack or poor response to asthma treatment despite correct inhaler technique and good adherence);
2. Presumed occupational asthma;
3. Persistent or severely uncontrolled asthma or frequent exacerbations;
4. Risk factors for asthma-related death – e.g., a near-fatal asthma attack (ICU admission or mechanical ventilation for asthma) at any time in the past; suspected or confirmed anaphylaxis or food allergy in a patient with asthma);
5. Evidence of or risk of significant side effects from treatment;
6. Symptoms suggesting complications or subtypes of asthma;
7. Additional responses for referral in children

6 - 11 years include: Doubts about the diagnosis of asthma; Symptoms or exacerbations that remain uncontrolled despite moderate-dose ICS with proper inhaler technique and good adherence; Suspected side effects of treatment (e.g., growth retardation); Concern for the child's welfare or well-being.

Conclusion. In view of the increasing incidence of under- and overdiagnosis, it is important to first discuss age-specific DD before making a diagnosis of "asthma", "viral wheezing" or "recurrent respiratory infections with BOS", and, if necessary, consultation with a pediatric pulmonologist is recommended if one or more of the indications mentioned in the article are present, or with a specialist from other pediatric specialties (if extrapulmonary pathology is suspected). Many patients have not benefited from the progress in the treatment of asthma in general and often lack even basic care. To improve asthma control, timely and accurate diagnosis, timely and adequate maintenance treatment, tailored to the individual characteristics and preferences of patients and the socio-economic status of the family and preferably with a reduced frequency of medication, as well as avoidance of asthma triggers and treatment of concomitant diseases, timely treatment of exacerbations, based on an easily implemented written, clear and accurate individual action plan, are of paramount importance. Evidence-based asthma treatment guidelines should be disseminated and implemented at national and local levels and integrated into health systems and clinical practice. Review after an asthma exacerbation is essential to optimize maintenance therapy and prevent future exacerbations, and a new treatment plan should be developed. Continuing education of pediatricians directly involved in the management of children with asthma, as well as education of patients and their relatives or caregivers in the correct use of technique and timely administration of medications, are key to improving asthma outcomes.

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